

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This issue is again a mixture of contributions, hopefully something for everyone! There is one paper that may be particularly interesting for J.UCS readers, because it discusses the applications of mashups, among other things to journals such as J.UCS! It is the paper by Narayanan Kulathuramaiyer. Reading it, you will find a first glimpse of what is in store for J.UCS, since some of the ideas in this paper will actually be implemented in our journal before the year is over.

There is also another bit of news: the word that J.UCS is now open access seems to spread since we receive more and more contributions from all parts of the world. This means that a yearly volume of J.UCS may well end up having more than 12 issues! Thus, the reputation of J.UCS is growing. Hence, consider submitting some good papers yourself - the open access and broad spectrum of published papers make the journal attractive to many readers so that the visibility of published articles is guaranteed.

Hope you enjoy the issue!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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